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ABSTRACT

Solutions such as -aaS (as a Service, such as Software or Platform as a Service) have become more and more trending. An increasing number of organisations are finding added value from such cloud-based solutions (Susan Moore, 2022). One particular trending -aaS is DaaS, the Desktop as a Service. This very recent technology is all about completely outsourcing desktops, which goes even further than similar cloud-based solutions such as Citrix, where only the operating system (e.g., Windows) is being simulated. By completely outsourcing desktops, computing power (such as powerful processors, video cards and so on) is not necessary to buy as an organisation since this power comes completely from the DaaS-provider. Within this paper, the costs of using DaaS in comparison to work 'the traditional way' is researched, as well as the (possible) security advantages, efficiency, and cost advantages that DaaS may bring. The flexibility of remote working is also discussed. To research these subjects, literature (archival) research as well as surveys and interviews are used.

Keywords

Desktop as a Service, digital transformation, small/medium enterprises, as a Service, cloud computing

INTRODUCTION

Different types of '-aaS' (as a Service) models are currently trending in the cloud world (Alshamaila & Papagiannidis, 2013). For example, the organisation Citrix, which hosts 'Software as a Service' or SaaS. Citrix provides a SaaS solution where windows is being simulated, and this is being sent to the end user. Clicks and typing inputs are then sent from the end-user to the server, providing a response. One other particular '-aaS' is the Desktop, or DaaS in short. DaaS has a lot in common with SaaS solutions. The big difference is that DaaS completely simulates a PC/laptop (or a desktop) which provides flexibility in the usage of software and desktops in contradiction to a SaaS-solution. Having a desktop completely outsourced and available in the cloud could mean fewer overhead costs, less worry about security (since the provider of the service makes sure security is up to date) and more flexibility in working from home. These are some examples of QoE (quality of experience), which is a key requirement

of DaaS (Md. Abu Layek, 2016). This paper gives insights in the properties of DaaS. Having DaaS also means monthly expenditures, and most importantly the requirement of a connection to the service provider, which needs to always be stable and fast to make sure the end-users of DaaS can work in the most efficient way. This stability still proves to be difficult to continually provide throughout the day (Hongdi Zheng, 2021). This paper focuses on this problem, what advantages DaaS could have for particularly Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs) and how the stability problem within the usage of DaaS could be addressed. Not a lot of research has been done towards DaaS, where especially SMEs could benefit from this very recent upcoming trend.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

As stated in the introduction, the stability of the connection between the DaaS service provider and the end-user of DaaS is not always consistent (Hongdi Zheng, 2021). This means possible slowness (low latency, the delay in the data transfer between systems) in the usage of this remote way of working. However, some possible solutions have been provided for this problem in previous research.

This paper dives deeper into the effect that DaaS will have on the upcoming digital transformation within SMEs, and its possible advantages and risks which the usage of DaaS brings. The research question for this paper is as follows:

Research question: What effect will DaaS have on upcoming digital transformations within SMEs?

To work on this research question, several sub-hypotheses have been created. By researching if these hypotheses are (partly) true, the final research question will be easier to answer. The hypotheses are as follows:

H1: SMEs are, by using DaaS, better able to focus on their primary processes/activities.

H2: Using DaaS is (on average) more costly in comparison to using traditional laptops/PCs within SMEs.

H3: Security within SMEs is improved when DaaS is fully implemented.

H4: With a stable latency (ping), DaaS provides a more efficient and flexible way of working for SMEs.

To answer these hypotheses, research has been done to dive deeper into the subjects. For this, sub-questions have been created. These sub-questions will be described in the following paragraph.

Knowledge gap

After exploratory research concerning different -aaS solutions and analysing the Gartner's "Emerging Technology Roadmap 2021-2023", it was concluded that there is a lack of academic research on cloud-based solutions within SMEs, especially on the new technology DaaS. The existing information is mainly focused on bigger organisations and other cloud-based solutions (e.g., SaaS). DaaS for SMEs is still in its early stages. Therefore, this research could be of added value to the current academic literature.

CONCEPTUAL MODEL

The conceptual model shows that focusing on the primary business processes/activities of SMEs are linked to two independent variables, one mediator and one moderator. The independent variables are the costs and the security of DaaS and 'usage of DaaS within SMEs' is the mediator. This states that the differences between using DaaS or using an alternative, influences the amount of focus an SME can or has on their primary business activities. The moderator is stable latency, which says something about the consistency of the connection between the end-user and the DaaS-provider. Both the costs decrease of using DaaS and the security improvements DaaS could bring is expected to increase the focus of SMEs on their primary processes.

Figure 1 Conceptual model

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

To answer the research question, some sub-questions have been constructed. These sub-questions focus on the necessary details of DaaS in SMEs.

H1: SMEs are, by using DaaS, better able to focus on their primary processes/activities.

In order to research H1, the following sub-question

have been created. This one is:

SQ1.1: How do different SMEs work with DaaS, and how do they compare to their previous state (not working with DaaS)?

This question focuses on the potential usage of DaaS within different SMEs where some research needs to be done.

H2: Using DaaS is (on average) more costly in comparison to using traditional laptops/PCs within SMEs.

The sub-questions for this hypothesis are as follows:

SQ2.1: How costly is DaaS (on average) for an SME organisation?

This question focuses on the cost of usage of DaaS for an SME. This question is necessary to answer with a logical and reasonable answer to the hypothesis.

SQ2.2: What is the difference in costs of using DaaS overusing the 'traditional' way of working within SMEs?

This question focuses on the cost of usage of DaaS in comparison to the 'traditional' way of working, that is, working with laptops/desktops which are costly since they need more (processor) power in contrast to the DaaS solution. Next to this, the difference between using DaaS and not using DaaS within SMEs are researched.

H3: Security within SMEs is improved when DaaS is fully implemented.

The following sub-questions have been created for the third hypothesis:

SQ3.1: How secure do SMEs think they will become by implementing DaaS, measured on a specific scale?

This compares the general 'feeling' of security within a organisation when DaaS could be implemented says something about the trust that SMEs (could) have in using DaaS.

SQ3.2: How much more security can DaaS provide SMEs in contrast to the 'traditional' way of working?

To give a general conclusion about the security advantages or disadvantages of using DaaS, this sub-question has been created.

H4: With a stable latency (ping), DaaS provides a more efficient and flexible way of working for SMEs

To answer this last hypothesis, the following sub-questions have been created:

SQ4.1: How can the usage of DaaS be stabilized so that end-users can depend on and trust using DaaS?

This first sub-question focuses on how the usage of DaaS can be optimized by always having a stable connection.

SQ4.2: How much more efficient and flexible can SMEs work with DaaS in comparison to the 'traditional' way of working?

This second sub-question focuses on the change (positive or negative) efficiency which DaaS could bring to SMEs in comparison to the 'traditional' way of working.

SQ4.3: What role does QoE play in making sure a stable connection between the DaaS-host and the end-user is realized?

This sub-question entails the perceived quality of experience (QoE) which measures how positive the experience with using DaaS is.

METHODOLOGY

The goal of this research was to collect a combination of qualitative and quantitative research to improve research validity and reliability. The qualitative research methods in this paper exist of archival research and interviews. The quantitative research of this paper exists of collected survey data.

Literature research

Existing literature has been conducted to get general insights into the current issues of DaaS and to support the theoretical questions. The existing literature used is academic research retrieved from three different databases: Web of Science, Google Scholar, and Scopus. To conduct research about DaaS the following keywords were used: "Desktop as a Service", "Cloud computing", "Infrastructure as a Service", "As a Service", and "Virtual desktop infrastructure".

To ensure reliable research the existing literature was selected on several requirements. After 2006 the first virtual desktop infrastructures had been under discussion, with professionals, proclaiming the benefits of cloud computing. One of them being Desktop as a Service. Therefore, the existing literature must be more recent than 2006 (Li, O'Brien, Zhang & Chai, 2014). Additionally, the existing literature was also based on the number of

cited references, the number of references used and the journal impact factor (JIF).

The outcomes of the conducted existing literature are the foundation of the results. Furthermore, in the discussion, the results from the existing literature are contrasted with the survey and qualitative results.

Survey research

The quantitative research part of this research consists of a composed survey. The survey was conducted to get insight into the computer systems that SMEs use for daily operations. A pilot test of the survey has been carried out on bachelor and pre-master students (n=9) with different study backgrounds to improve the survey quality. The survey has been forwarded on the seventh of November 2022 to Dutch SMEs. The data collected from the survey has been carried out using four steps. Defining the population, determining the sampling frame, sampling design, and sample size (n).

The first step before the data could be collected is defining the population (N). To population for the survey are all Dutch SME organisations (2.4 million) that use computer systems. The sample frame consists of the database of company.info (Company.info, n.d.) which is directly linked to the Chamber of Commerce database (KvK). Simple random sampling has been chosen as the sampling design for this research. This probability sampling design gives high generalizability to the data collection method. The methodology recommends conducting survey research with a 95% confidence level (z=1.962), a 5% margin of error, equal population proportion and a population (N=2.4 million). The recommended sample size is (n=385) (Taherdoost, 2017). Due to the limited time and scale of this research, the total number of respondents to the survey was 14 SMEs (n=14).

The survey mode was self-administered, electronic and web-based. The survey was randomly sent to (170) SMEs within the Netherlands. In total (14) SMEs responded to the survey. As a result, the survey response rate was (8,235%), rounded to the nearest integer. The survey consisted of 14 questions. Where eight questions were based on measured on 5-point Likert scale. Social desirability bias has been mitigated by keeping the survey data private and by creating a digital survey. Non-response bias has been mitigated by making all survey questions mandatory to answer before finishing the survey. Early and late respondents have been compared to check if there is any significant difference between the survey results. These solutions increased the survey's validity.

Cronbach's alpha has been calculated to assess the reliability and internal consistency of the set of survey questions. The measured Cronbach's alpha is 0.699 which means that the internal consistency is acceptable.

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
,699	8

Figure 2 Cronbach's Alpha

Interviews

Semi-structured interviews have been conducted to get insights into the practical questions. To manage the interviews an interview protocol was created. The interview protocol consists of four main subjects: setting the scene, warm-up questions, interview, and summarizing.

In the first step, an introduction was made, the interviewee was informed about the purpose of the research, and confidentiality is also mentioned. After that, warm-up questions are asked to the interviewee and the interviewee is mainly speaking. Thereafter the main questions of interest are discussed and based on the answers given, probing questions are asked. To finish the interview a summary with important information was given by the interviewee, to make sure everything was properly phrased. After the interview, the recording was transcribed.

The first interview group were Dutch providers/experts of DaaS to get insights how they look at the upcoming trend DaaS. The information from this interviewee population is used to expand/compare the existing academic literature found. Six consultancy organisations that provide DaaS were contacted. One consultancy firm responded and was interviewed. Additionally, another DaaS expert was interviewed, the expert had more than 10 years of experience with implementing DaaS at different organisations. However, it was indicated that this was preferably done on paper. Therefore, this interview was a structured interview. The second interview group were Managers/IT employees working in an SME, that recently had implemented a cloud-based solution. These interviews were conducted to view the experiences of changing from traditional (on-premises) systems to cloud solutions. Ten SMEs were asked for an interview. One interview was eventually conducted with an information manager at an SME where a cloud-based solution (SaaS) recently was implemented.

To preserve the validity of the qualitative research, the transcripts were sent to the interviewees afterwards. The interviewees provided comments on the transcript and made sure the answers given were

interpreted correctly. In addition, triangulation was admitted in the qualitative research. Interviews were conducted from two perspectives.

RESULTS

The research questions have been compiled and answered within the results chapter. Different methods from the methodology chapter have been used to answer the research questions.

Effects of DaaS on the primary processes/activities

H1: SMEs are, by using DaaS, better able to focus on their primary processes/activities.

This first hypothesis is answered through the (1.1) sub-question. The main goal of this question is to answer if the implementation of DaaS software within SMEs increases the focus on primary processes. Resulting in a more flexible, efficient, or cost-reductive way of working.

SQ1.1: How do different SMEs work with DaaS, and how do they compare to their previous state (not working with DaaS)?

Currently, most SMEs use some kind of -aaS service on a daily basis to support their day-to-day business. 57.1% of the survey respondents mentioned using direct cloud services such as Azure, AWS or Google Cloud which included IaaS, PaaS and SaaS services. And 92.2% of the survey respondents use Microsoft packages which offer SaaS services to support business activities. 64.3% (Mean: 3,71) of the respondents of the survey mentioned that the SME business they work for has difficulties with the up and downscaling of IT resources. 57.1% (Mean: 3.29) of the respondents expect that implementing DaaS fully within the SME would improve their focus on main activities. Lastly, 28.6% (Mean: 3.57) of the respondents think that the systems within the SME are below-average updated. Where 78.5% (Mean: 4.29) think that fully implementing DaaS will ensure that the computer systems within the SME will be up to date (see figure 3). Results consist of four survey questions that were measured on a five-point Likert scale.

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
AFSCHAAL_MOEITE	14	1	5	3,71	1,326
MATE_HBVL	14	1	4	3,29	,825
S_UTD_HUID	14	2	5	3,57	1,222
S_UTD_DAAS	14	2	5	4,29	,994
Valid N (listwise)	14				

Figure 3 Descriptive statistics SQ1.1

SMEs gain flexibility when cloud-based solutions are integrated within the SME, this is based on the interview that was conducted with a organisation that implemented cloud-based solutions within their

SME. The interviewee also mentions that the sharing of data and accessibility of data has also improved. This increased flexibility also results in an improved focus on the main activities and offers added innovation within the SME that was interviewed. The interviewee was not sure about implementing and using DaaS in the short term, because there was a lack of understanding about this new technology. But the organisation was interested and would maybe switch fully to DaaS after a thorough analysis.

From the interview and survey results, it can be concluded that there is an increase in focus on primary processes and activities within SMEs when DaaS is fully implemented. From the survey results, there is a significant result ($t(13) = 13.519$, $p < 0.001$) on the expected focus on primary activities within SMEs after DaaS is implemented.

Prior research also concluded that the use of DaaS and other cloud-based services offers SMEs more flexibility (Irwansyah, 2017). This increased flexibility gives organisations the ability to quickly change to shifting demands, like decreasing or increasing IT resources. SMEs that still fully rely on non-cloud-based systems are less flexible. Besides having the flexibility of up and downscaling IT resources, SMEs can better focus on their primary resources. Organisations that use cloud-based solutions overall increased the time to market for new products, through optimizing workflows and the integration of systems (Alshamaila & Papagiannidis, 2013). This means storing all data, tools, and blueprints in one central location (server). SMEs that work with DaaS also spend less time making manual backups. Because many DaaS providers offer automatic backup systems. In this case, if something happens to the data or systems. The files can be restored, without manually using data recovery software or physically recovering data from hardware devices. This reduces the chance of data loss. But this added flexibility comes with added costs of owning DaaS. These costs are discussed in the second hypothesis and flexibility is further discussed in the fourth hypothesis.

Costs of DaaS

H2: Using DaaS is (on average) more costly in comparison to using traditional laptops/PCs within SMEs.

This hypothesis can be answered through two sub-questions, where the focus will be on the cost of using DaaS vs the cost of not using DaaS, and what the difference in costs is between these two methods.

SQ2.1: How costly is DaaS (on average) for an SME organisation?

The cost of DaaS a DaaS-provider offers depends on a set of variables. According to the DaaS-consultant,

"several variables are important for calculating the cost of DaaS as a whole". The most important variables are the total amount of end-users, the total amount of users that may be logged into DaaS at the same time, the number of applications that are run on the DaaS-environment (and how much data these applications download/upload), and the amount of continuous (end)-user inputs are present. These variables all come down to one big requirement: the necessity of bandwidth.

Network bandwidth ensures data transfer across systems and determines how much information can transfer between systems. The lower the bandwidth the fewer data can flow through the systems, the higher the bandwidth, the more data can flow through it. The number of devices and programs used on these devices determines the amount of bandwidth an organisation needs. If organisations grow and use more digital services, the required bandwidth grows as well. The general rule of thumb: the more end-users DaaS has, the more bandwidth that is needed (Ben Town, 2014).

The cost of DaaS is not always less expensive than not working with a DaaS-solution. The DaaS-consultant said in an interview that "the costs of DaaS are mostly determined by the organisation who wants to implement DaaS, and especially on what scale. If the organisation wants to 'lease' laptops for example, or buy completely new ones, this increases the monthly price of what DaaS could cost. But if a organisation has recently purchased new laptops, or the current laptops are still sufficient, the DaaS-provider could also make a deal to include the current laptops in the service that the DaaS-provider could offer". One of the most important factors to the pricing of DaaS is the amount of money a organisation could and/or wants to spend on (the service of) DaaS. The more services DaaS brings to the SME, the higher the focus on the primary organisation processes becomes.

SQ2.2: What is the difference in costs of using DaaS overusing the 'traditional' way of working within SMEs?

To answer this question, the interview with the DaaS-expert is used.

The question of whether DaaS is 'less expensive in general' for SMEs will be looked at. According to the DaaS expert, DaaS can be cheaper than an on-premises IT solution. "When all factors are being taken into account, it (DaaS) could definitely be less costly". According to the DaaS expert, this is especially true when, for example, "an on-premises solution is upgraded towards a DaaS solution where this has the same benefits and guarantees as an MSP (managed service provider)-solution would offer. The scale advantages that an MSP brings, offers

lower costs per desktop".

The interview did not discuss the costs of a 'traditional way of working' versus a DaaS way of working. However, the paragraph above indicates that scale advantages of having DaaS offers a lower pricing per desktop usage. This means that, when an SME decides to implement DaaS, they would have increasingly better pricing of their laptops (less costly) versus when they don't use DaaS. Because of this, an opportunity for small SMEs with big growth potential arises. The bigger the organisation gets, the less expenses the organisation will have for owning increasingly more laptops (including all IT-management related tasks). For starting organisations, this approach could work even better since no initial costs of going from an on-premises to a DaaS solution have to be made.

According to the DaaS-expert, the costs of DaaS are fully (100%, specifically mentioned) compromised by the advantages DaaS brings. "When a careful calculation is done for a organisation, and especially for an SME, DaaS does not have to be more expensive". A organisation should first take inventory what they want from a DaaS solution before they move towards a final decision. When a organisation knows what it needs and what it currently owns, a careful calculation can be made where the (potential) differences in costs are determined.

Security of DaaS within SMEs

H3: Security within SMEs is improved when DaaS is fully implemented

This hypothesis can be answered through two sub-questions, where the focus will be on the expectation of SMEs on what scale they think DaaS can make an impact on the improvement of security within the organisation. Next to this, two interviews with a DaaS-experts will generate more insights into the security improvements DaaS could possibly bring.

SQ3.1: How secure do SMEs think they will become by implementing DaaS, measured on a specific scale?

The survey data showed no significant difference of security will occur, according to the employees working in SMEs. The survey data showed that seven employees expect no change in security by implementing DaaS. Six employees think the security will go up by one point on the Likert scale. One person expects that DaaS will reduce the security of implementing DaaS. In order to display these outcomes some descriptive statistics have been used (see figure 4).

The mean of the respondents of the current security

Descriptive Statistics						
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Variance
MATE_DAASBVL	14	1	5	3.64	.929	.863
MATE_HBVL	14	1	4	3.29	.825	.681
MATE_VERT_EXT_SYSDAT	14	1	5	3.21	1.122	1.258
Valid N (listwise)	14					

Figure 4 Descriptive statistics SQ3.1

of DaaS is 3.29, with the implementation of DaaS the mean changed to 3.64. However, the variance of the security after implementing DaaS is larger. This means that there is more dispersion within the answers of the respondents. The analysis of the data shows that there is no significance to conclude that DaaS will improve the security significantly.

The data of the survey also showed not all employees did not readily trust to outsource all data security to third-party providers. The interview with the organisation that recently implemented SaaS also came up with this argument. They elaborated that they had enough IT-knowledge with functional operators in-house. Therefore, it would be unnecessary to outsource this to a provider.

SQ3.2: How much more security can DaaS provide SMEs in contrast to the 'traditional' way of working?

One downside of DaaS and cloud computing is that the security and privacy are not yet secure. Providers say that that the data is secure, but it is important to understand that cloud computing still has its security challenges compared to the traditional way. With cloud computing, the applications and data move to large data centers. These data centers have only one security architecture (Eman, Hatem, Sherif, 2012). Therefore, it lacks regulations and legal uncertainty. Unauthorized access could be obtained by third parties (Mourato, 2021). By adding two-factor authentication and encrypting the data, security will be enhanced (Eman, Hatem, Sherif, 2012). However, SMEs could have some advantages if DaaS is implemented. SMEs are frequent targets of cyberattacks. SMEs often lack the resources and lack in-house knowledge to protect themselves against data breaches (Ozkan & Spruit, 2022). By implementing DaaS the security responsibilities are transferred to the providers of DaaS. Providers have more experience in data security and have a wide customer reach. Previous experiences related to security at other organisations can immediately be applied to all the other customers of the provider (Bryce, 2019).

The 'expert' and consultant both made clear that the security of SMEs will strengthen using DaaS. DaaS providers have a lot of knowledge and learn from all their customers, which later can be implemented. DaaS providers also need specific certifications to prove the privacy and security of data. Third, the DaaS providers also have ISO/CISO/FG devices with safeguarded processes to ensure the safety of

data. As a result, a crisis team will be on-site within a short time to solve the problem. Finally, the responsibilities of data leaks will mostly transfer to the DaaS provider. This, however, depends on how data is leaked and where the data leak occurred.

Efficiency and flexibility of DaaS within SMEs

H4: With a stable latency (ping), DaaS provides a more efficient and flexible way of working for SMEs

This hypothesis can be answered through four sub-questions (4.1 to 4.4).

SQ4.1: How can the usage of DaaS be stabilized so that end-users can depend on and trust using DaaS?

When implementing a DaaS system, it is important to choose a Managed DaaS Provider (MDP). These kinds of providers can address struggles, like striking the right balance between flexibility and stability. The MDP should implement failover mechanisms, which prevent users to work with downtime (Anunta Tech, 2020). An Intelligent and Reliable Transmission Scheme (IRTS) is a reliable and intelligent scheme to fix the problem of DaaS not being consistent in the response time and overall speed (Hongdi Zheng, 2021).

The ‘expert’ made clear that the usage of DaaS can be stabilized by making back-up connections. Go for high SLAs, reliable partners and get redundant connections, preferably physical north/south and fully (automatic) HA performed.

Some SMEs are start-up organisations that can grow to large organisations, e.g., when demand rises fast. One SME mentioned that it is important that DaaS is stabilized when demand rises. It was unknown if the DaaS provider has a stable connection for this case. However, the provider has a better uptime-guarantee for DaaS users.

SQ4.2: How much more efficient and flexible can SMEs work with DaaS in comparison to the ‘traditional’ way of working?

In times of a pandemic, SMEs were forced to work from home. For SMEs that utilize information technology, like DaaS, survived during the pandemic. Working with DaaS gives opportunities for employees to work from every desirable location (Lukman, 2020). This already shows that working with DaaS means more flexibility within SMEs.

Results of the survey made clear that 64.3% (Mean: 4.21) of SMEs use computers 8 or more hours per workday and 28.6% of the SMEs work with computers given by the employer. This implies that for a good portion of SMEs working with computers is probably an important part of their ‘traditional’ way of working. 28.6% (Mean 4.29) of the SMEs think that DaaS is an improvement for keeping their systems updated, in which case SMEs could work

more efficiently. 42.8% (Mean: 3.43) of SMEs think that DaaS is an improvement generally. See figure 5 for descriptive statistics of these results.

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
COM_GEBR_UUR	14	1	5	4,21	1,424
S_UTD_DAAS	14	2	5	4,29	,994
MATE_VERB_DAAS	14	2	5	3,43	1,089
Valid N (listwise)	14				

Figure 5 Descriptive statistics SQ4.2

Respondents made clear that with the use of DaaS you can work more efficiently, because tasks are outsourced. It also creates more flexibility since you can access it from every possible location. However, these advantages are not beneficial for every SME, since some respondents mentioned they are not working hybrid. DaaS deteriorates the efficiency and flexibility since you depend on the provider, there could be limited access for users, the process will become more complex, and it is uncertain if the connection is consistent.

Both the ‘expert’ and consultant mentioned that using DaaS improves efficiency since tasks are outsourced and organisations can focus on the important tasks. However, using DaaS deteriorates flexibility because it has a bad connection with other systems and services, and it is difficult to install new systems or make a change in systems. DaaS providers only started specializing in SMEs a short time ago, before that the focus was mainly on big organisations.

SQ4.3: What role does QoE play in making sure a stable connection between the DaaS-host and the end-user is realized?

QoE is defined as “the overall acceptability of an application or service, as perceived subjectively by the end-user”. Some examples of QoE are a fast boot-up time, single sign-on access control and configurability of the virtual environment (Md. Abu Layek, 2016). IRTS, what is mentioned before, is a form of QoE (Hongdi Zheng, 2021). When improving a stable connection, you improve QoE of DaaS.

DISCUSSION

A possible solution to the bandwidth stability problem could be a backup connection, for example, a DNS-server which makes remote working in different places more stable or an extra 4/5G connection which acts as a backup option for when the regular connection fails. This could be negotiated in the contract (SLA) with the DaaS provider, to make sure the best end-user experience is realized. However, there is not much information gathered around this subject. In future research, this needs to be examined further. This could for example be done by interviewing different DaaS providers. A side

node: this solution may not be applicable to all SMEs worldwide. Since countries in Africa may have a completely different (digital) environment and setup, specific research needs to be conducted in order to say something about this solution.

Data security is difficult to measure within organisations. Therefore, the “expectation” of employees was used as a measure of construct in this study. Employees expect that the security of the data will improve slightly. Cloud solutions showed some gains for SMEs. Data security will be outsourced to a third-party provider. Therefore, SMEs, in particular IT personnel, can focus more on primary processes/activities. However, the employees indicate that they do not fully trust third-party providers with all their data security. This may ensure that SMEs will select solutions that only partially transmit data security to a third-party provider. This could cause problems for DaaS as a solution in the future, because here the data security will be transmitted fully to the third-party provider.

Limitations

In this conducted research paper, there are some potential limitations. The first limitation was the limited time frame for conducting the quantitative and qualitative research for this study. This resulted in a lower number of survey respondents than the methodology recommends. The recommended sample size is (n=385) (Taherdoost, 2017). The lower number of survey responses (n=14) retrieved may lead to unreliable and less generalizable results.

The second limitation is that only three interviews were conducted in this research (n=3). Therefore, no significant comparisons could be made between different interviewees' perspectives. In addition, within the timeframe, it was not feasible to find an SME that recently implemented DaaS. However, an SME which implemented SaaS was interviewed to get insights into the transformation from an on-premise to a cloud-based infrastructure.

The third limitation was that the DaaS experts could have been biased and therefore indirectly influence the results of the interview. Because it is in the consultant's best interest to speak positively about DaaS implementations for SMEs to gain publicity. Additionally, one interview was done on paper means that misunderstanding could have occurred, and probing questions were not possible.

The fourth limitation is about the difficulties with reaching SMEs that already have implemented DaaS services. Because this technology is new and not yet standardly used within SMEs it was difficult to gather archival data, survey respondents and interviewees that could give more insight into the before and after implementation of DaaS technology.

The fifth limitation is about the generalizability of the research. The data that has been gathered in this research paper is collected from respondents and interviewees from The Netherlands. Besides that, archival research was based on developed countries as well. This makes this study generalizable for SMEs within developed countries. The research is less generalizable for developing countries. Because the research did not account for factors that do play a role within developed countries. Therefore, lack of infrastructure, not having access to an internet connection or not having access to electricity within SMEs is not taken into account.

The sixth limitation is about the scope of the research. Within this research paper, there has been done limited research on the topic of security within DaaS. Most of the research on security is based on archival research on cloud-based solutions. For the surveys and interviews, only the perceived computer system security within SMEs has been measured. This measure does not represent the exact system's security within an SME.

CONCLUSION

Research question: What effect will DaaS have on upcoming digital transformations within SMEs?

To answer the research question, the sub-questions are used. For the first hypothesis, it can be concluded that there is an increase in focus on primary processes and activities within SMEs when DaaS is fully implemented.

From hypothesis two it follows that DaaS could mean less expenses for laptops (and general IT-management related tasks), for especially SMEs. The bigger the SME becomes, the less IT-management costs the SME will potentially have.

From hypothesis three it follows that data security will not be ensured better or worse. However, the IT department's workload shifts to the primary processes/activities of the SMEs.

From hypothesis four it follows that it depends on the needs of the organisation whether DaaS provides a more efficient and flexible way of working for SMEs. Since providers focused more on large organisations, it was not an addition for SMEs in the past. Recently providers focused more on the needs of SMEs, thus, it can be an addition.

When looking at all the outcomes of the research regarding the hypotheses it can be concluded that Desktop as a Service has a big growth potential within SMEs. However, the specific impact highly depends on the situation the SME is currently in. In general, however, it can be stated that the benefits for a small or starting SME are higher than for a 'bigger' SME. This does not imply that the benefits for bigger SMEs are too small to make a difference,

since this depends on the (IT)-targets of the SME and if they think the benefits outweigh the costs of implementing DaaS.

The costs of DaaS also highly depend on the situation an SME is currently in versus the situation they want to go to. If they already have great IT internally, such as in a situation where high-end laptops were bought recently (for example less than a year ago), the monthly costs of DaaS may be lower than for SMEs which are currently using very outdated IT. Next to this, the ways in which DaaS could be implemented also affects the pricing. An SME could choose to keep their own laptops, or "lease" them from the DaaS provider, which makes another difference in the pricing.

The effect of DaaS on upcoming digital transformations within SMEs will highly depend on the targets the SMEs have set for themselves for the future of their organisation. However, DaaS offers a big growth potential for both starting and small SMEs as well as bigger SMEs in fewer terms.

Future research

Firstly, in this research, the industry sector of the SMEs is not specified. Further research could make a specific model for which industry sectors a DaaS solution would be more relevant. Additionally, research could provide a model of how those SMEs could implement a DaaS solution.

Because of the current time and data gathering limitations, it was not possible to measure the average predicted increase in the focus on primary processes/activities within SMEs when DaaS is implemented. In future research, this question could be researched to get more insight into more specific results.

The costs of DaaS need to be researched deeper in future work. Right now, the specific costs are not generalizable because of different sizes of SMEs, where it would be beneficial for the research to look at individual sectors of SMEs and different sizes of SMEs, and compare the possible costs for each sector to come to deeper insights.

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APPENDIX A: INTERVIEW PROTOCOL PROVIDER DAAS**Objective**

Collect information on Desktop as a Service from providers in the Netherlands. Find the pro and cons and insights in how they think it will affect Small to Medium Enterprises.

ID	Topic	Info/description	Prio
Part I: Introduction (2.5 min)			
Getting to know each other and manage mutual expectations. Inform about the purpose of the interview and the use of the results. Ask for consent to record/process the interview and use the results in paper			
1.1	Introduction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Briefly introduce yourself Explain that the interview is going to take +/- 30 minutes 	I
1.2	Motivation for interview	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Paper for the conference Information Management on Digital Resilience 	I
1.3	Expectation management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The goal is to draw the experience of the interviewee If desired, we can send the final result of the paper Invitation to the conference on 16 January 	II
1.4	Consent	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Consent form Tell data processing is done anonymously Ask for permission to record/process 	II
Part II: General information (5 min)			
Information about interviewee, the organisation and their work area			
2.1	Organisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Some Background information of the organisation Are current customers of the provider SMEs 	I
2.2	interviewee	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Personal background (studies/previous work) What is the function of the interviewee within the organisation 	II
Part III: Information Desktop as a Service (10 min)			
Gather as much useable information about Desktop as a Service			
3.1	Desktop as a Service in general	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Short explanations of Desktop as a Service 	II
3.2	Desktop as a Service in Small and Medium enterprises	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Is it commonly used in small and medium enterprises How costly is Desktop as a Service How secure is it and how can it be retained 	III
3.3	Pros Desktop as a Service	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> What are the pros of Desktop as a Service 	III
3.4	Cons Desktop as A Service	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> What are the cons of Desktop as a Service 	III
Part IV: Disruption in Desktop as a Service (10 min)			
Gather information about responsibilities of the providers of Desktop as a Service to the organisations			
4.1	Disruption in Desktop as A Service	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Who is responsible if the cloud has malfunctions What if the provider goes bankrupt, what happens with the Service and data Who is responsible for data leaks within the organisation 	III
Part V: Closing (2.5 min)			
Closing of the interview and show appreciation of the interview			
5.1	Summarizing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Repeat the purpose of the interview and research. Summarize key findings 	I
5.2	Follow-up	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Explain how information from the interview is going to be used Ask if the interviewee is willing to review the transcript, to avoid any misunderstandings Any questions to us from the interviewee 	II
5.3	Sign off	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> If on ID 1.3 is agreed to send the final results, exchange contact information Thanking the interviewee for their time 	I

APPENDIX B: INTERVIEW PROTOCOL SMES**Objective**

Collect information on cloud-based solutions from small medium enterprises in the Netherlands. See how they view cloud-based solutions within the organisation.

ID	Topic	Info/description	Prio
Part I: Introduction (2.5 min)			
Getting to know each other and manage mutual expectations. Inform about the purpose of the interview and the use of the results. Ask for consent to record/process the interview and use the results in paper			
1.1	Introduction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Briefly introduce yourself Explain that the interview is going to take +/- 30 minutes 	I
1.2	Motivation for interview	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Paper for the conference Information Management on Digital Resilience 	I
1.3	Expectation management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The goal is to draw insights of the interviewee If desired, we can send the final result of the paper Invitation to the conference on 16 January 	II
1.4	Consent	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Consent form Tell data processing is done anonymously Ask for permission to record/process 	II
Part II: General information (5 min)			
Information about interviewee, the organisation and their work area			
2.1	Organisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Some Background information of the organisation 	I
2.2	Interviewee	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Personal background (studies/previous work) What is the function of the interviewee within the organisation 	II
Part III: Old IT structure (5 min)			
Gather information about the current IT structure and knowledge about Desktop as a Service within the organisation			
3.1	Old IT structure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> How was the old IT structure constructed Were you pleased with the old IT structure 	II
Part IV: implementation SaaS (5 min)			
Gather information about negative points about the current IT structure			
4.1	Implementation DaaS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Why did the organisation choose for SaaS above other structures How did the implementation of SaaS go generally Were there any hang-ups in the implementation process 	III
Part V: Pros and cons SaaS (5 min)			
Explain Desktop as a Service			
5.1	Desktop as a Service	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> After the implementation did you had any negative thoughts of SaaS After the implementation did you had any positive thoughts of SaaS Would you go back to the old IT structure if it was possible 	III
Part VI: Closing (2.5 min)			
Closing of the interview and show appreciation of the interview			
6.1	Summarizing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Repeat the purpose of the interview and research. Summarize key findings 	I
6.2	Follow-up	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Explain how information of the interview is going to be used Ask if interviewee is willing to review transcript, to avoid any misunderstandings Any questions to us from interviewee? 	II
6.3	Sign off	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> If on ID 1.3 is agreed to send the final results, exchange contact information Thanking the interviewee for their time 	I